

Neha Verma
Sheetal Ajit Patil

Composition, Mechanism of Action and Therapeutic Potential of Bothrops Venom

Abstract

The Bothrops genus is a group of aggressive venomous snakes, widely distributed across the South American continent and are responsible for majority of the envenomings, making their venoms medically relevant. Bothrops species snake venoms vary in their composition, mechanism of action and their effects due to genetics, age, habitat, diet, gender. This narrative review article focuses on in-vitro and in-vivo studies restricted to Bothrops species venoms and their compositions, effects, mechanisms of action and the advancements in exploring the therapeutic potential of Bothrops venom. The research articles were selected by searching databases including Google Scholar, PubMed, ResearchGate and Science Direct. The chronological review that follows is based on 32 articles with a focus on studies conducted on Bothrops species venoms published between 2000 and 2024. Research in Toxinology necessitates the integration of multiple research tools due to the complex nature of snake venoms, their mechanisms of action and potential therapeutic properties. Further novel research designs are need to fully leverage the therapeutic potential of snake venoms.

Keywords: *Bothrops asper*, *B.lanceolatus*, Snake venoms, metalloproteinases, serineproteinases, LAAOs, PLA2s

Introduction

Envenomation from snakebites is a worldwide public health concern that primarily impacts rural communities in tropical and subtropical regions of Africa, Asia, Latin America, and Oceania. According to the WHO estimates, over 2.5 million snakebite envenoming incidents occur annually, resulting in 400,000 amputations and more than 100,000 deaths. Every year, some 25,000 incidents of snakebite are documented, and more than 100 people die from them in Brazil alone. The suggested treatment for envenomation caused by snakebite involves injecting intravenously certain anti-venoms, derived from horses that have received an immunization^{1,2}.

Snakes classified under the Bothrops genus, belonging to the Viperidae family, cause 84% of envenomation cases worldwide, with around 0.4% fatality rates³. Some common snakes under Bothrops genus include *Bothrops alternatus*, *B. asper*, *B. atrox*, *B. brazili*, *B. jararaca*, *B. jararacussu*, *B. lanceolatus*, *B. moojeni*, *B. neuwiedi* and *B. pictus*.

Mainly found in South and Central (Latin) America, Bothrops species cause venomous ophidian accidents, with *B. jararaca* and *B. asper* being common in Brazil and Costa Rica^{4,5}. In Brazil, they cause 90% of all recorded snakebites⁶. Bothrops snakes in Brazil cause over 70% of reported snake bites. *B. lanceolatus*, a venomous pit viper native to the French Caribbean island of Martinique, causes an average of 30 human envenomation cases annually^{5,7,8}. The genus includes thirty species, distributed across seven groups⁹. Peru's diverse snake species, including nine endemic species and 24 spread over neighbouring countries of Latin America, contribute to the country's rich biodiversity. Ophidism, a major cause of morbidity and

mortality, is primarily reported in rural forest regions⁹.

The complicated pathophysiology of these snake venoms includes both local and systemic effects. Their venoms contain enzymes, toxins, and biogenic amines that trigger toxic effects and stimulate the immune system and cause haemorrhage, myonecrosis, altered cardiovascular function, edema, and coagulation disorders, due to the combined effects of many venomous substances^{10,11,5,12}.

Permanent local tissue damage, systemic alterations, acute kidney injury, disability, or amputations, and complex inflammatory reactions have also been noted^{13,14}. The pathogenic events behind these reactions remain unclear due to animal models not reproducing human clinical symptoms¹⁵. Understanding the mechanisms behind the inflammatory reactions and the resulting leukocyte recruitment is crucial for developing new treatment strategies¹⁴.

Venoms are complex mixtures of toxic components with highly variable concentrations. Variability in venom composition is an adaptation to facilitate prey capture, digestion, and predator evasion. The Brazilian Amazon region's *B. atrox* venom, responsible for most human envenomations, has been studied for gene dispersal and evidence suggests the role of the Amazon River in causing in situ divergence¹⁶. Venom variability, particularly in *B. atrox*, is also linked to its ontogenetic development and geographic distribution¹⁷. Studies have investigated intraspecific variation linked to ontogeny or geographic dispersion, although it remains unknown if habitat diversity in nearby geographic regions affects the variability of venom or the symptoms of human envenomation¹⁷. Such variation in

venom composition often affects treatment and antivenom development¹.

Methodology

This narrative review focuses on qualitative information that is available throughout the various medical research materials. Articles confined to studies conducted on Bothrops species venoms that were published from 2000 to 2024 were reviewed. Databases like Google Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct and Research Gate were used to browse and select the articles. Keywords used were *B. lanceolatus*, Bothrops species, Snake venoms, in vitro, in vivo. Fifty articles were reviewed out of which 32 were selected based on their content with special focus on Bothrops species snake venom composition, mechanism of action, in vivo and in vitro studies.

Discussion

Composition: Immunogenic proteins and non-immunogenic substances make up snake venoms. They contain around 50-200 components, of which dominant families include Snake venom metalloproteinases (SVMPs), Phospholipases A2 (PLA2s), Snake venom serine

proteases (SVSPs), Snaclecs (Snake C-type lectins) and L-amino acid oxidases (LAAOs)¹⁸.

SVMPs which make up 30 to 60% of the Viperidae family, impact haemostasis by triggering prothrombin and coagulation factor X and defibrinogenesis. The SVSPs, a group of enzymes, make up 10-30% of Viperid venom. PLA2s, found in multimeric structures, constitute 5 to 45% of viperid venom and play various roles in envenomation¹. They are basic proteins that release creatine kinase into plasma. Myotoxins may induce direct damage to the plasma membranes of muscle cells, or they can cause indirect damage to vessels and ischemia via the activity of metalloproteinases found in snake venom. Two isolated myotoxins, Asp49-PLA2 and Lys49-PLA2, showed catalytic, anticoagulant and indirect haemolytic activity¹⁹. *B. atrox* venoms also contain a hyaluronidase (Hyal-Ba), homologous to other hyaluronidases, which is metal-dependent for its activity²⁰.

LAAOs found in bacteria, snake venoms, fungi and green algae, catalyze the oxidative stereospecific deamination of alpha-keto acids, producing ammonia and hydrogen peroxide¹. LAAOs are proteins that are glycosylated and include a 3-4% carbohydrate moiety that constitutes up to

12% of the total molecular mass. The crystal structures of LAAOs from *B. atrox* and *Vipera ammodytes* have been discovered to include zinc binding sites. The glycan moiety of SV-LAAOs consists of core-fucosylated, biantennary, and bis-sialylated dodecasaccharides. These moieties' functions include attaching LAAO to the cell surface and raising the content, which triggers apoptosis. Different snake species' LAAOs showed differing substrate specificity²¹.

Lectins, now called Snaclecs that are carbohydrate-binding proteins and have various biological activities, including agglutination of cells, detection of liposome-conjugated lectins, cell surface sugars, immunoglobulins, tumorigenic cells, and enzymes. Glycoproteins in *B. moojeni* venom include BMooL and BmjMIP¹. (Refer to Table 1).

Variability: The composition of Bothrops species' venoms varies significantly due to factors like diet, genetics, age, gender, geographic distribution, or seasonality²² and this variability is an adaptation to facilitate prey capture, digestion, and predator evasion. Many studies have been conducted and the effects and mechanisms of action have been studied.

Activity of venom components like PLA2, proteolytic, and LAAOs is known to vary from species to species. Evidence suggests that *B. jararaca* venom has a moderate PLA2 activity and LAAO activity while *B. jararacussu* has high haemolytic activity and moderate PLA2 activity. *B. moojeni*, has been found to have low haemorrhagic action and high proteolytic activity while *B. neuwiedi*, has high PLA2 activity and LAAO activity. *B. alternatus* venom has a low PLA2 activity, but presence of an acidic PLA2 component is responsible for its lethal effects on mice³.

Significant differences in biological activity and venom composition were found among *B. atrox* snakes from four different habitats of the Brazilian Amazon, namely forest, floodplains, pasture, and degraded area. Venoms of pasture and floodplain snakes had higher abundance of SVMPs, with the most complex fractions mainly composed of P-I SVMPs, acidic D-49 PLA2 and basic K-49 PLA2, SVSPs, and C-type lectins (snaclecs). The predicted phenotype was more procoagulant and less haemorrhagic¹⁷. Snakes from the floodplains had venoms with reduced SVMP activity and increased SVSP catalytic activity¹⁶. Among and within *B. asper* populations, there has been intraspecific regional and ontogenetic variation in the relative abundances of SVSP, D49-PLA2 against K49-PLA2, and PI-SVMP versus PIII-SVMP in Costa Rica's Caribbean and Pacific regions²³. Phenotypic variability based on the habitat of Bothrops species' venoms suggests that the venom composition and functional variability may represent the species' local adaptation to different prey communities in different habitats¹⁶.

In vivo experimental model to compare the effects of adult and juvenile *B. lanceolatus* venoms shows that juvenile venom induces pulmonary thrombosis to a greater extent than adult venom. Effects of juvenile and adult *B. lanceolatus* venoms on classical clotting tests showed no alterations in aPTT and PT, and a substantial decrease in fibrinogen levels after an intravenous infusion. Rotational thromboelastometry parameters were affected by juvenile specimens, while adult venom only affected FIBTEM parameters²⁴.

Significant intraspecific variation in the electrophoretic profile of the individual venom specimens of the same species, *B. moojeni*, reiterates the variation in the venom phenotypes in various snake genera²⁵.

Differences in venom composition between sexes of the same species that exhibit sexual dimorphism has also been noted in certain studies. Females exhibited stronger electrophoretic profile than males of the same species while greater LAAO activity was seen in the males. Increased proteolytic activity of female *B. moojeni* venom may be attributed to the need for a robust defence mechanism during offspring generation²².

Mechanism of action: Bothrops species' venoms hydrolyze the elements of the extracellular matrix and are also capable of directly hydrolyzing inflammatory mediators. *B. lanceolatus* venom causes a systemic thrombotic condition characterized by localized inflammation, restricted bleeding, and necrosis due to low hyaluronic activity^{5,15}. Multiple systemic macro-thrombosis may be due to reduced ability of vWF to bind to collagen types I and III, but increased vWF ability to bind to collagen types VI, which may represent a significant pathophysiological mechanism causing multiple thrombotic events².

Bothrops venoms, especially of *B. asper*, induce leukocyte accumulation by upregulating adhesion molecules, such as L-selectin, PECAM-1, LFA-1, ICAM-1 and beta 2 integrin chain, which play role in leukocyte migration, leading to ROS (Reactive oxygen species) overgeneration and enhanced H2O2 production. Cytokines like IL-6, IL-1 and TNF- α cause expression of adhesion molecules, hepatic proteins and T and B cell activation¹⁴. Plasma concentrations of Vitamin E decreased in every patient, possibly due to systemic ROS overgeneration. In snakebite victims, antioxidant medication with vitamins E and C may reduce systemic oxidative stress²⁶.

Purified PLA2 activates the complement system, causing a strong inflammatory reaction and favourable conditions for thrombus formation. A possible contributing factor to complement activation is the reduction of the complement regulators DAF and CD59 on the erythrocyte membrane¹⁵.

S.No.	Bothrops venom components	Action	Reference
1	Snake venom metalloproteinases (SVMPs)	I. Affects haemostasis by inducing defibrinogenesis and activating coagulation factor X and prothrombin. II. Indirect damage to vessels and causes ischemia.	<i>Journal of Venom Research</i> . 2021 <i>B. jararacussu</i> . <i>Biochimie</i> . 2000 Aug 1
2	Snake venom serine proteases (SVSPs)	Procoagulant activity.	<i>Toxins</i> . 2024 Jul 1
3	Phospholipases A2 (PLA2s)	I. Mycotoxins cause direct damage to plasma membrane of muscle cells. II. Myotoxins showed catalytic, anticoagulant, and indirect haemolytic activities.	<i>B. jararacussu</i> . <i>Biochimie</i> . 2000 Aug 1
4	L-amino acid oxidases (LAAOs)	I. Catalyze oxidative deamination of alpha-keto acids, producing hydrogen peroxide and ammonia leading to cell apoptosis II. Inhibition of coagulation	<i>Journal of Venom Research</i> . 2021
5	Snaclecs (Snake C-type lectins)	Carbohydrate-binding proteins that lead to agglutination of cells, detection of cell surface sugars, enzymes, immunoglobulins, tumorigenic cells, and liposome-conjugated lectins.	<i>Journal of Venom Research</i> . 2021

Table 1: Effects of major components of Bothrops venom

Significant correlation has been elicited between PLA2 activity and edematogenic effects in Bothrops species venoms⁶. *B. lanceolatus* venom cleaves two proteins, MIG and IL-12, the chemotactic factors for T-lymphocytes, which can lead to a compromised adaptive immune response and production of specific antibodies⁵.

B. lanceolatus venom has also shown high level of cytotoxicity in human immortalized cell lines HaCaT keratinocytes and EAhy926 vascular endothelial cells, similar to *B. jararaca*⁵. *B. jararaca* venom also elicits cytotoxicity in various tumour cell lines by inducing mitochondrial membrane depolarization and increased catalase activity²⁷.

HT venomics and integrated bioassays have shown that *B. alternatus*, *B. jararaca*, *B. atrox* and *B. neuwiedi* venoms have a procoagulant activity primarily due to SVMPs and SVSPs, and anticoagulant activity presumably due to PLA2s¹⁸.

In vivo studies: *B. jararaca* and *B. asper* venom injected intraperitoneally in mice resulted in a prolonged leukocyte migration into the peritoneal cavity and elevated nitrite concentrations in macrophages. IFN-g release into the peritoneal cavity also increased, suggesting IFN-g's function as a modulator of macrophage iNOS production⁴. *B. asper* venom induced noticeable haemorrhagic activity and a comparatively milder myonecrosis. The fluids released from the mice administered with *B. asper* venom showed typical local effects along with higher amounts of endoplasmic reticulum (ECM) proteins because of hydrolysis by SVMPs and endogenous MMPs. Higher proteinase activity in the exudates can be attributed to myocyte damage. *B. asper* venom does not identify VEGF, suggesting that systemic vascular leakage may be mediated by inflammatory mediators released in tissues¹⁵.

Lys-49 PLA2 and Asp-49 PLA2 from *B. asper* venom injected into mouse peritoneal cavity increased vascular permeability, indicating that vasoactive mediators originating from mast cell granules are involved. Asp-49 MT-III (catalytically active enzyme) has been found to be more potent than Lys-49, suggesting that enzymatic phospholipid hydrolysis is significant in this process. One of the adhesion molecules in the Selectin family is upregulated in expression by both PLA2s²⁸.

When BaP1, a P-I class SVMP from *B. asper* venom, is injected into a mouse's peritoneal cavity, it results in a local inflammatory response that lasts for a while and releases inflammatory cytokines including TNF-a and IL-1. Selectin family adhesion molecule LECAM-1, which mediates the event, is expressed at a higher level due to upregulation by BaP1²⁹.

Effects on platelet aggregation: Active SVMPs, acidic PLA2s and Baltergin, a haemorrhagic PIII SVMP, have a suppressive effect on platelets aggregation with ristocetin and collagen or ADP as inducers. The high content of SVMPs in *B. alternatus* venom may be the result of several interactions with platelet receptors or ligands³⁰.

B. pictus venom contains LAAO (an L-amino acid-oxidizing) enzyme called Bpic-LAAO, a homodimeric protein that has been reported for various biological effects, including apoptosis, cytotoxicity, inhibition, platelet aggregation, haemolysis and edema of coagulation. Like other SV-LAAOs, Bpic-LAAO causes edema in mice and, in a dose-dependent manner, prevents PRP-induced platelet aggregation⁶.

Potential therapeutic properties: Bothrombin, a thrombin-like enzyme found in *B. brazili* and *B. atrox* exhibits amidolytic and gelatinolytic, coagulatory and fibrinogenolytic activities. Serine proteinases from both the specimens exhibit diverse metal cofactors and chelators showing calcium as a requisite for the action of enzyme. The impact of serine proteinases on tubule formation in endothelial cells shows a two-time increase in interconnecting events upon stimulation. They have the ability to modulate angiogenesis, finding an 80-90% survival rates of cells after 48 hours of therapy. Serine proteinases from Bothrops species have pro-angiogenic properties¹².

The venom of the *B. alternatus* snake produced a novel isoform of L-amino acid oxidases (LAAOs) called Balt-LAAO-II, which exhibits a strong affinity for L-Leu and catalytic activity against L-Met. In vitro investigations for the Balt-LAAO-II's cytotoxicity against human cancer cells, show a dose-dependent cytotoxic action primarily involving cell lysis. Such isoforms may prove useful in cancer treatment and pharmacology³¹.

Rat thymic endothelial cells' adhesion and tube-forming abilities have been shown to be influenced by P-I metalloproteinases from *B. pauloensis*, indicating anti-angiogenic characteristics. One important venom component, LAAO, has shown anti-tumour activities in many cancer cell lines by generating H2O2 and causing caspase-mediated apoptosis triggered by reactive oxygen species in endothelial cells, keratinocytes and leukemic cells. The prospective use of LAAOs' regulated apoptotic effects in cancer treatment is worth considering. Further studies are required to explore such therapeutic avenues³².

Conclusion

Understanding the complex nature of Bothrops venoms and its effects is necessary to develop efficient and cost-effective treatment modalities for managing the rising envenomings.

Such understanding requires enhancing research in toxinology by integrating multiple research tools for a comprehensive knowledge base that can be leveraged to take advantage of the potential therapeutic action of venoms.

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Dr. Neha Verma,

P.G. Scholar, Dept. of Homoeopathic Materia Medica,
Bharati Vidyapeeth Homoeopathic Medical College.

Ph: 6397750502

Email: drnehaverma02@gmail.com

Dr. Sheetal Ajit Patil

Professor, Department of Homoeopathic Materia Medica,
Bharati Vidyapeeth Homoeopathic Medical College,

Katraj, Pune, India - 411043.

Email: drsheetalvk1@gamil.com

Cover: Composition, Mechanism of Action and Therapeutic Potential of Bothrops Venom: The *Bothrops* genus, a group of venomous snakes widely distributed across South America, is responsible for the majority of envenomings in the region. The chronological review of research articles underscores the integration of multiple research tools highlighting the complex nature of *Bothrops* venom, its mechanisms of action, and its potential therapeutic properties.